

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC IN THE PSYCHOLOGY AND PSYCHE OF CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The main task in working with children is to create conditions for comfort and creative freedom in music lessons. Only in such conditions is it possible to develop a constant interest in musical activity and its creative potential. The specially selected repertoire, due to the targeted pedagogical influence, not only achieves psycho-emotional correction, but also creates conditions for the development of creative abilities in music lessons.

Listening to children's music is carried out in the process of musical-pedagogical work, during the participation of children in all types of children's musical activities, in leisure evenings and holidays. The teacher traditionally devotes part of the music lesson to listening to music, using certain methods and techniques in organizing it. The educator also begins to listen to music, to organize the process as an activity, or to help children perceive musical works independently. Children and family listen to music with their parents, go to concerts, go to musical performances, and so on.

The main task of shaping a child's personality is the comprehensive and harmonious development of the child. This task is accomplished through music education. N.K. Krupskaya describes the importance of art in nurturing a child's personality: "Through art, we need to help the child understand their thoughts and

feelings, think more clearly, and feel more deeply." Relying on pedagogy. defines the concept of musical education and development according to these rules. The main task of shaping a child's personality is the comprehensive and harmonious development of the child. This task is accomplished through music education. N.K. Krupskaya describes the importance of art in nurturing a child's personality: "Through art, we need to help the child understand their thoughts and feelings, think more clearly, and feel more deeply." Musical upbringing of a child is the purposeful formation of the child's personality, interest, need and aesthetic attitude to music through the influence of musical art. A child's musical development is the result of shaping a child's personality in the process of active musical activity. Many scholars and educators believe that the sense of musical rhythm does not depend on education and development

(L.A. Brenboim, K. Sishor, N.A. Vetlugina, etc.). Musical upbringing, the tasks of shaping the child's personality are subordinated to the general goal of comprehensive and harmonious upbringing of the child's personality and are built taking into account the specificity of the musical art and the age characteristics of preschool children.

These rules define the concept of music education and development. The ways and means of organizing music perception in preschool children proposed by researchers today, in our view, require a certain systematization of the teacher's actions, given that perception is focused on a particular aspect of child development. Widely used traditional methods and techniques also need to be updated. Let us specify the possibilities of the process of music perception in the integral development of the preschool child and etc. Here are the developmental aspects that enable children to understand music:

Emotional development;

Socialization and culture;

Development of basic cognitive processes - thinking, memory, attention, imagination, curiosity, perception itself;

Artistic types of children's activities - a specially organized process of perception of music, which affects the development of speech, play, visual skills and creativity.

Pedagogical technology is a tool of professional activity teacher. The essence of pedagogical technology is that it has a clear stage, each of which includes a specific set of professional actions, which allows the teacher to predict the intermediate and final results of their

professional and pedagogical activities in the design process.

Musical upbringing plays an important role in the aesthetic and moral formation and formation of a child's personality. With the help of music, children get involved in cultural life, get acquainted with important social events. In the process of perceiving music, children develop cognitive interest, aesthetic taste, and expand their horizons. Children who play musical instruments are usually more literate than others. Music provides both imaginative thinking and spatial imagery, as well as a habit of daily hard work. It is necessary to start dealing with children from the age of four. Regular music exercise improves memory and stimulates children's mental development, Canadian scientists say. They received the first evidence of a link between music lessons and the ability to concentrate. But despite all the inconveniences of the initial phase of teaching children to play musical instruments, previous generations of parents have tried to teach children music. While music lessons required not only the constant hard work and willpower of the children, but also the patience of the parents, only a few of them became professionals, but they taught all or almost all and considered it necessary.

The child who interacts with music develops in all directions, the child's appearance improves, harmonious relationships are established. In the process of singing, not only the musical ear develops, but also the singer's voice, resulting in the vocal motor apparatus. Musical rhythmic movements result in the correct position, coordination of movements, their flexibility and flexibility. The child can feel the character, mood of a

musical work, sympathize with what he hears, show emotional attitude, understand the musical image, distinguish between good and evil, and thus join in various types of artistic activity. Children also have the opportunity to listen, compare, and evaluate the most obvious and understandable musical events. The influence of music has a direct effect on a child's emotions, shaping his or her moral character. The influence of music is sometimes stronger than persuasion or direction. By introducing children to a variety of emotionally meaningful works of art, we encourage them to empathize. A song about the homeland evokes a feeling of love for the homeland. Round dances, songs, dances of different nations arouse interest in their traditions, cultivate international feelings. The richness of genres in music helps to perceive heroic images and lyrical mood, cheerful humor and cheerful dances. The various emotions that arise in the process of perceiving music enrich children's experiences, their spiritual world.

Collective singing, dancing, games, when children are full of common experience, make a great contribution to solving educational problems. Singing requires a concerted effort from the participants. General experiences create a favorable environment for individual development. An example to friends. The common

passion and joy of execution activates fearful, indecisive children. For those who are deprived of attention, the change in other children's self-confidence and successful performance serves as a brake on negative demonstrations. Such a child can be offered to help partners, thereby cultivating humility and at the same time developing individual abilities. Music lessons influence the general culture of a preschooler's behavior. Different types of activities (singing, listening to music, children playing musical instruments, switching to music, etc.) change the focus, intelligence, reaction speed, coordination, children's voluntary actions requires the song, start and end it on time; in dances, in games, to be able to move, to obey music, to run faster, to give up the desire to chase someone. All this improves the inhibitory processes, affects the will of the child. We emphasize that the effectiveness of pedagogical technology always depends on the sequence of the teacher, the gradual development of a particular mental process, children's activities, the child's age characteristics. Therefore, before designing authoring technologies for organizing the process of musical perception of preschool children, it is necessary to study the specifics of the process of perception in general and the peculiarities of the formation of this type of musical activity of preschool children.

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